

Organotin(IV) Dithiocarbazates

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The ligational behaviour of dithiocarbamates (R_2NCSS^-) like other dithio-anions, such as dithiophosphates, dithiocarboxylates and xanthates towards metallic as well as organometallic moieties has been investigated extensively due to current activity in the study of sulphur-nitrogen ligands. Metal complexes of an analogous ligand dithiocarbazate ($H_2NNHCSS^-$), its N-substituted derivatives and their S-methyl esters, possess various industrial uses¹⁻³.

The behaviour of these ambidentate dithiocarbazate anions which can coordinate either through the two sulphur (I) or through the terminal nitrogen and thiol sulphur (II) atoms, towards organometallic moieties, has not been studied. This communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of organotin(IV) derivatives of dithiocarbazic and 3-phenyldithiocarbazic acids.

Results and Discussion

Di- and tri-organotin(IV) derivatives of dithio-

carbamic acid (Hdctz) or its 3-phenyl derivative (HPdctz) were obtained by the metathetical reaction between stoichiometric amounts of R_2SnCl_2 or R_3SnCl and the ammonium or hydrazinium salt of the acids. The elemental analyses of the product correspond to R_2SnL_2 or R_3SnL (L =anion of the acids) composition (Table 1). A change in the stoichiometric amounts of the reactants leads to inconsistent analyses of the products. The new organotin(IV) dithiocarbazates are sharp melting yellow to orange coloured crystalline solids. Organotin(IV) derivatives of unsubstituted dithiocarbamic acid are soluble in the solvents with high dielectric constant, such as methylcyanide or nitrobenzene, while the 3-phenyl dithiocarbazates are fairly soluble in common organic solvents. Cryoscopic and conductance measurements indicate monomeric and nonelectrolytic nature of these compounds in solution.

The ir spectra of ammonium dithiocarbamate and hydrazinium salt of 3-phenyldithiocarbamic acid exhibit two bands (at 3 335, 3 250 and 3 290, 3 180 cm^{-1} respectively) due to NH stretching vibrations⁴. No significant change in the position and intensity of these bands is observed in the spectra of all the organotin(IV) derivatives of 3-phenyldithiocarbamic acid as well as in those of $R_3Sndctz$. However, the spectra of organotin(IV) derivatives of unsubstituted dithiocarbamic acid exhibit broad and very weak

bands at 3 200–2 900 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to ν_{NH} coupled with aromatic or aliphatic ν_{CH} vibrations. The observed lowering in ν_{NH} frequency and the absence of any absorption due to ν_{S-N} in the lower region of the spectra may be explained by the presence of inter-molecular hydrogen bonding⁵ in $R_nSn(dctz)_{4-n}$ compounds which also accounts for their insolubility in common organic solvents. The ν_{C-N} frequency is lowered in the organotin(IV) derivatives relative to the respective parent dithiocarbamate anions which may be taken as an evidence of monodentate coordination of the CS_2 group in these compounds. Furthermore, the spectra of all the organotin(IV) derivatives exhibit clear splitting and positive shifting of the $\nu_{as}CSS$ band identified in the region 965–1 025 cm^{-1} in the parent dithiocarbamate anions, irrespective of the nature and number of the organic groups in the organotin moiety. Since NCS_2 group in the dithiocarbamate anion closely resembles that in N,N -dialkyldithiocarbamate, we find, contrary to the conclusion of Haines and Louch³, the splitting and shifting of this band to be characteristic of uninegative monodentate coordination of CS_2^- group to organotin(IV) moieties. The conclusion is in accordance with the earlier reports^{1,5,7} on organotin(IV) dithiocarbamates, metal dithiocarbazates and esters of dithiocarbamic and dithiocarbamic acids excluding thereby the disulphur chelation of $dctz$ and $Phdctz$ to organotin(IV) moieties.

In the lower ir region an intense sharp band in the region 330–410 cm^{-1} , present in the spectra of all the organotin(IV) dithiocarbazates and conspicuously absent in those of the dithiocarbamic acid salts, may safely be assigned to ν_{Sn-S} . The spectra of aryltin(IV) derivatives are characterised by the presence of a band of medium intensity at ~ 440

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	
		C	H	H	Sn	as CSS	Sn-S
$Ph_3Sndctz$	85	50.90 (49.92)	4.32 3.97	6.43 6.13	25.60 25.96)	992, 1 018	370
$(p-Tolyl)_3Sndctz$	173d	52.62 (52.93)	4.66 4.85	5.12 5.61	23.52 23.77)	998, 1 019	362
$Bz_3Sndctz$	145	52.30 (52.93)	4.24 4.85	5.20 5.61	22.98 23.77)	995, 1 010	340
$n-Bu_3Sndctz$	139	38.50 (39.31)	7.40 7.61	6.80 7.05	29.23 29.88)	992, 1 012	409
$Ph_2Sn(dctz)_2$	133	35.05 (34.51)	3.94 3.31	11.94 11.50	24.30 24.36)	998, 1 022	350
$Bz_2Sn(dctz)_2$	88	37.60 (37.29)	3.68 3.91	10.32 10.87	22.95 23.03)	990, 1 009	360
$Me_2Sn(dctz)_2$	150	12.90 (13.23)	3.48 3.33	15.90 15.43	32.79 32.69)	970, 990	330
$n-Bu_2Sn(dctz)_2$	105	26.50 (26.85)	5.20 5.41	11.80 12.53	27.08 26.54)	990, 1 008	360
$Ph_3SnPhdctz$	85–90	56.30 (56.31)	4.36 4.16	4.97 5.25	21.97 22.26)	996, 1 020	330
$n-Bu_3SnPhdctz$	130	47.90 (48.21)	7.01 7.24	5.31 5.92	24.82 25.08)	999, 1 023	410
$Ph_2Sn(Phdctz)_2$	128	48.27 (48.84)	3.52 3.78	8.43 8.76	18.90 18.56)	998, 1 021	410
$n-Bu_2Sn(Phdctz)_2$	121	43.90 (44.08)	5.50 5.38	9.40 9.35	19.28 19.80)	996, 1 021	265

cm^{-1} due to the out-of-plane bending vibration of aromatic ring attached to tin atom⁸ while the absorption in the region $260\text{--}280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed⁹ to the asymmetric Sn—C (phenyl) stretching vibrations. In case of butyltin(IV) dithiocarbazates, asymmetric and symmetric Sn—C absorptions are identified¹⁰ at ~ 597 and $\sim 510\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while these vibrational modes give rise to bands at ~ 570 and $\sim 530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of dimethyltin(IV) derivatives.

Experimental

Hydrazinium salts of dithiocarbazic and 3-phenyldithiocarbazic acids and ammonium dithiocarbazate were obtained by the reported method¹¹. The salts were characterised by their melting point and analyses corresponding to $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNHCSS}^- \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNH}_3^+$: $\text{H}_2\text{NNHCSS}^- \cdot \text{NH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$: $\text{H}_2\text{NNHCSS}^- \cdot \text{NH}_4^+$ stoichiometries.

Organotin(IV) chlorides were reacted with stoichiometric amounts of the freshly prepared appropriate dithiocarbazic acid salt suspension in the non-aqueous solvent under anhydrous condition. In a representative experiment, a solution of Ph_2SnCl_2 (1.715 g, 5 mmol) in benzene (20 ml) was added dropwise to a suspension of hydrazinium salt of 3-phenyldithiocarbazic acid (2.92 g, 10 mmol) in the same solvent under stirring. The mixture was stirred further for 5–6 h resulting orange coloured solution. The residual solid was filtered off and petroleum-ether (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$) was added to the concentrated filtrate and left overnight. The resulting crystalline solid was then washed with dry diethyl ether and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride under reduced pressure.

Organotin(IV) derivatives of unsubstituted dithiocarbazic acid were obtained by refluxing organotin(IV) chlorides with ammonium dithiocarbazate in acetonitrile. In this case acetonitrile was used as a solvent, due to the insolubility of the resulting complexes in common organic solvents, which made their separation from the reactants difficult. When hydrazinium dithiocarbazate was used in place of ammonium dithiocarbazate the yields were poor.

In all the compounds, tin was estimated gravimetrically as tin(IV) oxide. Microanalyses for C, H and N were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solutions of all the compounds was measured in nitrobenzene at room temperature ($30 \pm 0.5^\circ$) and their molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic method using benzene or nitrobenzene as the solvent. Ir spectra (KBr or CsI) were recorded on a PE 521 spectrophotometer.

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